

ENMA 283 Spring 2007 Team Project

Applying Genetic Algorithms and Neural Networks to FTIR Spectrograms to Measure Biodiesel Blend Ratio

Tony Roder, Sharath Tadepalli, Jignesh Talati, John Meyer
Dr. Mark Polczynski

Introduction

Biofuels are fuels derived from living organisms (vs. fossil fuels, e.g., petroleum and coal). Biofuels represent a renewable energy source; can often be derived from waste organic materials, and have the potential to reduce dependence on non-local energy sources. Biofuel sources include corn, soybean, waste vegetable oil, farm and food processing waste, etc.

This research applies to biodiesel fuel derived from soy oil, which can replace petroleum-based diesel fuel. Biodiesel is typically used at a number of biodiesel/diesel blend ratios (e.g., 2%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 50%, 100%). It is important to be able to accurately determine the biodiesel/diesel blend ratio for a particular batch of fuel for several reasons, including:

- Engine performance optimization,
- Calculation of tax rebates for biodiesel use.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) is an analysis tool that can determine the constituents of a material by measuring the attenuation of light by the material over a range of infrared frequencies (various constituents attenuate light at characteristic frequencies). The purpose of this project was to apply genetic algorithms and neural networks to FTIR spectrographic information to measure biodiesel blend ratio.

This research was conducted per a general “knowledge discovery in databases” (KDD) methodology: 1) goal identification; 2) target data set generation; 3) data preprocessing, 4) data transformation; 5) data mining; 6) interpretation and evaluation; 7) recommendations.

Goal Identification

Typical FTIR spectrograms for biodiesel, diesel, and a 50/50 mix of biodiesel and diesel fuels are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

The spectrograms exhibit several attenuation peaks at frequencies characteristic of the two types of material. The goal of this work was to determine the blend ratio for a sample of fuel of unknown blend ratio from the magnitudes of the FTIR attenuation peaks. No knowledge of the constituents of the biodiesel and diesel base fluids or their relationship to the attenuation peaks was presumed here – the goal was to determine blend percent simply by analyzing the magnitudes of the major peaks.

Target Data Set Generation

Five-gallon containers of commercially-available biodiesel and diesel were obtained. Biodiesel/diesel samples were prepared with the following biodiesel percent: 100, 66.66, 50.36, 34.03, 33.73, 20.85, 11.64, 6.21, 3.24, 1.70, 0.90, 0.00. Succeeding samples were prepared by cutting preceding samples approximately in half, thereby avoiding the need to measure and add small quantities of materials. FTIR spectra for nine samples of each concentration were obtained.

All samples were analyzed in a Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrometer and their spectra recorded as ASCII files using Perkin-Elmer spectrum software. Prior to each data collection exercise ($9 \times 12 = 108$), the spectrometer had to be calibrated to set up instrument background spectrum; this would then be the reference for the IR spectrum of the collected sample. The device had to be cleaned repeatedly before testing to eliminate, reduce or account for possible errors caused as a consequence of human operator contamination, machine induced errors and environmental factors. These errors were both systematic and random. The contamination check was vital as test plate impurities

induced noise into the background spectrum which affected the peak values of the IR spectrum of the samples. Cleaning was, therefore, essential and involved treating the over head steel alloy plate with hexene, soap and water with rapid blow drying before and after each sample was set up for analysis.

However, true to the real world, about 20% of the 108 samples collected failed the contamination check. On close observation it was noted that the higher SNRs resulting from contamination lowered the peak values of the sample (subtractive effect from negative correlation) on the spectrum as seen in Figure 2 below.

The data was then recorded for each concentration with 9 samples per concentration. Visual inspection revealed 7 distinguishable and statistically significant peaks which were then chosen from each spectral plot, seen in figure 3 below. The plot graphs the change in accentuation energy for each range of wavelength that the machine identifies. Corresponding pairs of wavelengths and peak values were then collected i.e. 7 pairs of wavelength-energy sets per sample extending over a fixed concentration. A random selection was made to split the combined data set into validation and training with 66.67% samples in the training mode and 33.33% in the test mode.

Figure 2

Figure 3: FTIR Spectrum with Identified Peaks

Data Preprocessing

While problems of missing data were not encountered in this scenario, corrupt and noisy data was seen in abundance, to the tune of 20% or approximately 22 samples. The noisy data was still considered statistically significant to understand the effect of the background spectrum and error induced noise in the sample spectrum. The samples were thus incorporated into the study after all. Further, the goals of the project were to identify and understand how well neural networks and genetic algorithms work in recognizing the effect of wavelengths in explaining blend ratio of the bio-diesel samples through mathematical iterative curve fitting procedures; how well would they be able to cluster and classify the difference between bio-diesel and diesel, the sub-clusters within the bio-diesel samples based on concentration percentages and the binary clusters of samples which have passed and failed the contamination check. The idea was to check for the robustness and accuracy of these two learning programs, hence, the entire data set was used for the study with the limited sample size of $108 \times 7 = 756$ peaks.

Data Transformation

Consequent to the objective of the study, effect of sample size was not deemed influential. Outliers were found but all were assumed to be statistically significant and hence included. The dependent variable, accentuation energy, was normalized to have scaled values between 0 and 1 while the explanatory variable of wavelength was left untouched. Contamination check was assumed sufficient enough to account for possible

effects of in-lab air pressure, temperature, humidity, suspended particle and wind level changes.

Partial smoothing of the data collected was seen with the spectral plot generated by the IR spectrometer. Heavy correlation was noticed between SNR and spectral peak plot. However a correlation transformation was not deemed required as the noise and its subsequent effects were one of our research interests. Further, the data was not Gaussian normal and we did not expect the residuals of the curve fitting to be one. The regression approach to the curve fitting was more tilted towards using the R^2 statistic (measures the extent of fit or how well the given independent variable was able to explain the linear change in the dependent variable) in identifying the usefulness of NN and GA for identifying blend ratio. Focus on the residual statistics and error terms to test for error term independency, normalcy of error terms, appropriateness of fit and other such linear regression diagnostics were thus not immediately appropriate. Hence, no data transformation on Y or X or on both was done.

Data subsets were finally created with a random pick of the total samples. As described earlier, 3 of the 9 samples per concentration totaling 36 across all concentrations were used for validation while the remaining 6 of 9 samples per concentration adding up to 72 across all concentrations were used for training.

Data mining – KDD structure

Chart 1: KDD Process Flow Diagram

Data Mining – Genetic Algorithms

Genetic Algorithms (GAs) describe a technique used to extract information from multiple data sets, usually represented in binary strings. This technique relies on coding evolutionary characteristics such as mutation, “gene” crossover, generations, and replication. By simulating genetic functions and applying them to rapid random solution generation a regression curve fit may be obtained on data that may not have outwardly apparent physical groupings or characteristics. This method allows correlation of data in a context that can discover solutions to problems with much less resource reliance and training than more traditional regression methods.

Chart 2: Genetic Algorithm Process Flow Diagram

The GA technique starts with a group of data, generally broken up into Xs and Ys. The X data is used by the GA to correlate different data sets (Xs) to specific Ys. The total data set is then broken into two groups, training and validation. The training data subset is used to teach the algorithm and allow it to evaluate the fit of its generated solutions by use of the R^2 statistic. The solutions determined from the training subset are then applied to the validation subset to determine the fit of the solution on previously

unseen data, thus preventing a lookup-table type solution. In order to generate solutions the GA goes through four general steps as follows:

1. The GA will first create a population of random binary coded solutions. These solutions will generally be of some predetermined length, complexity (allowed mathematical operations) and number. Once the population of generated solutions exists, the GA will input all of the training data subset Xs and calculate the corresponding Ys.
2. Next the GA will evaluate each program on the total data set via a fitness function. This step determines how well the calculated Y matches the given Y from the training data subset. In our study this fitness function was the R^2 statistic.
3. Once each program has a R^2 value the GA will undergo the following sequence to change or evolve the solutions:
 - a. The GA will first save the “best” solutions by deleting 50% of the solutions with the lowest R^2 values, this is called selection.
 - b. The remaining solutions are then replicated to restore the population to the original size.
 - c. After replication the programs undergo crossover. During crossover the solutions pair off. Each pair of programs then separates at a random point and the front or back end of the programs swap between the pair. Creating slightly different programs than the originals.
 - d. A mutation phase is then completed in which random bits may be forced to a new value.
4. Steps 2 and 3 are repeated until a satisfactory R^2 value is achieved for both the training and validation data subsets or the GA completes the maximum number of generations specified by the user.

A pictorial representation of this simplified process is outlined in Figures 4 - 8. The data set in this example is represented by a single eight bit binary string. A binary least-is-best fitness operator is used (any non-matching bits = 1). The original solution population size in this example is 4.

For this example our data set or end goal = Target String (TS). This represents the program that will give us zero error.

TS = 01101001

Step 1: Create a population of bit strings that represent solutions

- Our GA system creates 4 random 8-bit strings
G1:01011010
G2:01011011
G3:10111000
G4:10110011

Step 2: Apply the Fitness Operator

Recall, we will use the **binary least-is-best** fitness operator:

Iter.	Bit Strings								Fit.	
Start	TS	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	
	G1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	
	F1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	3
	G2	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	
	F2	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	6
	G3	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	
	F3	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	5
	G4	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	
	F4	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	4
	Total									18

Figure 4

- F's are the fitness strings for each guess G.
- "Fit." is the fitness of the string.
- G1 and G4 are the most fit strings.
- "Total" is the total fitness of the population.

Step 3: Apply the Selection Operator, Replicate, Crossover, Mutate

- Save G1 and G4 and throw out G2 and G3
- Old G1 goes into new G1 (keep G1)
- Old G4 goes into new G2 (keep G4)
- New G1 and G2 go into new G3 and G4 (*replicate* G1 and G4)

Iter.	Bit Strings								Fit.	
Start	TS	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	
	G1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	
	F1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	3
	G2	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	
	F2	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	4
	G3	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	
	F3	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	3
	G4	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	
	F4	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	4
	Total									14

Figure 5

- Select random crossover points on G1 – G2 pair, and then on G3 – G4 pair.

Iter.	Bit Strings									Fit.	
Start	TS	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0		
	G1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0		
	F1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	3	
	G2	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1		
	F2	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	4	
	G3	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0		
	F3	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	3	
	G4	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1		
	F4	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	4	
	Total										14

Figure 6

- Swap the front ends of the string pairs to create G' new guesses.

1	TS	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	
	G1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	
	G1'	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	
	F1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	3
	G2	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	
	G2'	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	
	F2	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	4
	G3	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	
	G3'	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	
	F3	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	4
	G4	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	
	G4'	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	
	F4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
	Total									

Figure 7

- Randomly mutate bits in the G' (new) strings

1	TS	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0		
	G1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0		
	G1'	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0		
	F1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	3	
	G2	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1		
	G2'	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1		
	F2	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	5	
	G3	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0		
	G3'	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0		
	F3	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	4	
	G4	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1		
	G4'	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1		
	F4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	
	Total										14

Figure 8

Step 4: Repeat steps 2 and 3 until a satisfactory fitness level is achieved.

The primary focus of this portion of the study was to determine if GAs could reliably curve fit the FTIR peak data, discussed previously, into accurate calculated biodiesel percentages. Secondly it was desired to determine if GAs could classify the samples as either “contaminated” or “clean”. The GA software chosen for these tasks was Discipulus Lite™ (Discipulus™). Discipulus™ is capable of generating both regression analysis and classification functions. Although the classification function is less developed than the regression analysis, Discipulus™ is capable of placing members of a data set in one of two user defined classifications. Discipulus™ has many design features that allow it to operate very quickly to analyze possible solutions for the defined problem. Of these design features the following were altered to determine the affect on the final outcome:

- Population size
- Max program size
- Initial program size
- Crossover rate (homologous vs non-homologous)
- Mutation rate
- Instruction set (allowed mathematical operators)

Design Options and Optimal Settings

After several iterations it was determined that population size, initial program size, mutation rate, and crossover rate (both homologous and non-homologous) had no significant effects (as modified for this study) on the best fit of the outcome after a sufficient run period. Max program size and instruction set had the largest impact on overall fitness level after a sufficient run period. Typical run times were on the order of 72 hours. That being said the solutions G' tended to converge to an acceptable level of error

faster with larger population sizes, a larger initial program size, a higher mutation rate and a larger instruction set. Discipulus™ attained comparable results for all runs after a sufficient time as long as the design features were not changed in a manner that would purposefully hinder the calculations. By changing the max program size to a very small value or decreasing the instruction set to exclude most common mathematical operations it was possible to achieve unsatisfactory results and thus prevent Discipulus™ from converging on a desired solution. Based off of this data the optimum settings for this study, when time was not an issue, were the defaults on all variables except max program size and instruction set. Max program size should be increased to at least 1024 and all options available selected for the instruction set. Selecting primarily default values, unless there is a significant impact as described above, is considered optimum for two reasons. First, accepting the default values saves time on start up and still achieves adequate results. Secondly, by accepting the default values it is very unlikely that operator changes made to the design features will hinder Discipulus™ in developing an adequate solution.

Interpretation and Evaluation – Genetic Algorithms

Discipulus™ proved very effective at curve fitting the seven FTIR peaks from our supplied data to the sample biodiesel/diesel blend ratios. The best program achieved a combined training and validation $R^2 = 0.9826$. The best team achieved a combined training and validation $R^2 = 0.9911$. When all corrupt and noisy samples, approximately 22, were removed from the data set (labeled as Good Data Only) the fits improved to: best program $R^2 = 0.9994$ and best team $R^2 = 0.9996$. The team solutions showed a better fit in all cases and will be used for all further analysis. Figures 9 – 12 display various results from Discipulus™ in the form of calculated biodiesel concentration vs sample biodiesel concentration. All figures contain a trendline that was curve-fit through the data points for ease of analysis. The ideal solution would yield a trendline with a slope of 1.0 and a y-intercept of 0.0.

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

As expected the data indicates that Discipulus™ had a much higher accuracy in determining the concentration of biodiesel when corrupt and noisy samples were removed. This proved especially useful in the lower concentration region of the study where the differences in concentrations were much smaller. This is significant, however, because many biodiesel users face similar situations in which the concentrations of the offered biodiesel products will be 0%, 2%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 50% and 100% etc... As you can see at the lower end of the concentrations there are many more offerings with much closer concentration values making accuracy a paramount concern.

As discussed earlier Discipulus™ was then used to distinguish the corrupt and noisy samples from their “clean” counterparts. This classification problem proved extremely important given the accuracy differences ascertained from the noisy vs good data in the regression analysis. Discipulus™ was able to achieve a hit rate of 100% on all training and validation data given a probability for each class fixed at 0.5 to eliminate bias. The confidence level of Discipulus’™ classification was high on all but 10 samples of the total 108; these ten exhibited a confidence level of 50%. These low confidence samples corresponded to those that marginally failed the contamination check and were “cleaner” than most failures but still affected by the noise induced from the contamination present.

Based off of the data presented above it can be concluded that:

1. GAs, in particular Discipulus™, represent an adequate method for identifying biodiesel/diesel blend ratios given FTIR sampling data.
2. The accuracy with which GAs can determine the blend ratios is significantly affected by the noise and contamination levels present at the time of sampling.
3. GAs were able to identify corrupt and noisy samples with a high confidence more than 90% of the time.

Applications of Genetic Algorithms

Several applications of Genetic Algorithms (GAs), as referenced by the makers of Discipulus™ are outlined below. It is easy to see that GA software can be used for a myriad of extremely complex tasks.

- Prediction of corporate bankruptcy in apparently healthy firms
- Network Intrusion Detection
- Tumor Classification using DNA microarray data
- Geological data mining for oil and gas
- Discrimination of unexploded ordnance from digital geophysical mapping signal
- Reverse-engineering legacy applications
- Refinery and plant control programs
- DNA Array classification
- Financial market prediction
- Prediction of corporate financial well-being one year into the future
- Environmental engineering

Data Mining – Neural Networks

Neural networks are very sophisticated modeling techniques capable of modeling extremely complex functions. In particular, neural networks are nonlinear (a term which is discussed in more detail later in this section). For many years linear modeling has been the commonly used technique in most modeling domains since linear models have well-known optimization strategies. Where the linear approximation was not valid (which was frequently the case) the models suffered accordingly. Neural networks also keep in check the curse of dimensionality - the problem caused by the exponential increase in volume associated with adding extra dimensions to a (mathematical) space.

Neural networks are very easy to use because *they learn* by example. The neural network user gathers representative data and then invokes training algorithms to automatically learn the structure of the data. Although the user does need to have some heuristic knowledge of how to select and prepare data, select an appropriate neural network, and interpret the results, the level of user knowledge needed to successfully apply neural networks is much lower than would be the case with some more traditional nonlinear statistical methods.

Basic neural networks model is described in Figure 13.

The Heart of Neural Nets - Your Basic Perceptron...

Figure 13

Applications of Neural Network

Neural networks are applicable in virtually every situation in which a relationship between the predictor variables (independents, inputs) and predicted variables (dependents, outputs) exists, even when that relationship is very complex and not easy to articulate in the usual terms of "correlations" or "differences between groups." A few representative examples of problems to which neural network analysis has been applied successfully are:

- **Detection of medical phenomena.** A variety of health-related indices (e.g., a combination of heart rate, levels of various substances in the blood, respiration rate) can be monitored. The onset of a particular medical condition could be associated with a very complex (e.g., nonlinear and interactive) combination of changes on a subset of the variables being monitored. Neural networks have been used to recognize this predictive pattern so that the appropriate treatment can be prescribed.
- **Stock market prediction.** Fluctuations of stock prices and stock indices are another example of a complex, multidimensional, but in some circumstances at least partially-deterministic phenomenon. Neural networks are being used by many technical analysts to make predictions about stock prices based upon a large number of factors such as past performance of other stocks and various economic indicators.
- **Credit assignment.** A variety of pieces of information are usually known about an applicant for a loan. For instance, the applicant's age, education, occupation, and many other facts may be available. After training a neural network on historical data, neural network analysis can identify the most relevant characteristics and use those to classify applicants as good or bad credit risks.

One of the two techniques used in neural networks is Widrow – Huff learning rule, more commonly known as backpropagation learning. This method is based on supervised learning, in which we present the network with a set of training data with known input-output relationships. Figure 14 explains the Widrow – Huff learning rule.

So, how did we do this Widrow-Hoff?

1. Start-Up:
 - 1.1. Create the Input/Output Table.
 - 1.2. Set all Weights to 0.
 - 1.3. Select a value for n.
2. Repeat Until all $t - R = 0$ for all combinations:
 - 2.1. Randomly select row in Truth Table.
 - 2.2. Calculate weight changes.

For real networks:
 $t - R < \text{"allowable error"}$

A design
decision

Figure 14

As mentioned above, backpropagation learning is a supervised learning method. It is also possible to do unsupervised learning with neural networks. This unsupervised learning is called a Kohonen network or Self Organizing Map. Below is how a Kohonen network works.

- Given sets of raw data, we specify how many clusters we want to group the data into. Then we see how well this mapping works.
- So, we make no prior assignments on what sets of data fall into what classifications.
- But for iDA™ (Software used for Neural Networks, explained later) implementation, we make a guess of how many clusters there are.
- Of course if we get bad results, we could repeat this process for other values for the number of clusters.

Below are the pictures explaining a Kohonen Network and how it works.

Kohonen Network = Self-Organizing Map

- **Every** input node is connected to **every** network node.
- Network nodes are **not** connected.
- There is no **“output”** per se.
- Every network node is an **“output”** i.e. a cluster.
- Every link has a **weight** (not shown).
- Network is typically shown as **$i \times j$ matrix**.

Figure 15

How does it work?

1. You start by stating how many clusters you **want**, say **C**.
2. Then you create a matrix of nodes with **many more** clusters than what you want, i.e. $(i \times j \gg C)$ nodes.
3. You attempt to map all of the data sets into **all** of the $i \times j$ nodes by varying the input/output weights.
4. You **reward*** a node every time it **wins*** a data set by modifying its weights.

Then...

* We'll define how a node wins and how we reward it in a few slides.

Figure 16

How a Node Wins

A node **wins** when its weights more closely **match** the input values. Match means, of course that the RMS **error** between the **input** and **weight** values is the lowest.

So, here's an example network...

Figure 17

iData Analyzer (iDA™)

The primary focus of this portion of the study was to determine if NNs could reliably curve fit the FTIR peak data, discussed previously, into accurate calculated biodiesel percentages. Secondly it was desired to determine if NNs could classify the samples as either “contaminated” or “clean”. The NN software chosen for these tasks was iDA™. iDA™ is data mining tool capable of both supervised and unsupervised clustering. iDA™ is an add-on to Microsoft Excel. A picture of the interface follows this discussion. Below is a partial list of features incorporated with the ESX™ learning model:

- It does not make statistical assumptions about the nature of the data to be processed.
- It supports an automated method for dealing with missing attribute values.
- It can point out inconsistencies and unusual values in data.
- For supervised classification, ESX™ can determine those instances and attributes best able to clarify new instances of unknown origin.
- For unsupervised clustering, ESX™ incorporates an optimized evaluation functions that encourages a best instance clustering.

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Figure 18

- Neural networks require separate data sets for training and validation.
- You take (approximately) half of your data to train the network. This data set is the training data.
- “Training the network” means “calculating the weights”.

- Then, you take the rest of the data and run it through the network to see if it predicted the correct output. Call this data set the validation data.
- In iDA™, you can have all the data in 1 file and the program separates the data for the two different uses.
- One drawback is iDA™ has no way to run the validation separate from the training. To do validation on a separate data set, you have to divide the data up into two files and then run the resulting model on the second file.

Design Options and Optimal Settings

Design functionalities, process controls and optimal constraints for the knowledge based learning process within the artificial neural networks architecture were based on random selection and a trial and error based update procedure. A training accuracy deemed permissible on visual inspection controlled the number of runs and number of iterations within each run. The effects of presence of hidden layers, their number and the inherent nodes within a hidden layer, input layer and output layer are described below. To begin with, the learning rate, choice of kernel function, number of nodes per layer and admissible error for the supervised learning module used for the process were default values provided by iDA™. Both unsupervised (via Kohonen networks) and supervised (via backpropagation algorithm) learning methods were applied to test for their relevance, applicability and for comparison. No changes were deemed necessary to these default values when acceptable limits of tolerance and error were obtained. However, several runs were made to reach these limits given a variable number of epochs per run for the (mathematical curve fitting) iterative polynomial least squares optimization exercise.

Interpretation and Evaluation – Neural Networks

Overall, iDA™ was only somewhat effective at accurately curve fitting the seven FTIR peaks to the blend ratio of the biodiesel/diesel samples. Using backpropogating networks, the best model resulted in an R2 of 0.9693, about 2% less than genetic algorithms. For Kohonen networks, the results were not possible to graph against a predicted value. The results were measured by how well the model divided the samples into nodes, which in this case was only 17% (2 out of 12). The remaining samples were intermixed and had no unique nodes. Finally, the data was analyzed by each type of neural network for contamination. Backpropogating networks once again proved to be the most effective neural network at analyzing the data, correctly classifying 99% of the data.

In data acquisition using backpropagation learning, five variables were used to find the best settings including: Data Quality, Hidden Layer 1 (HL1), Hidden Layer 2 (HL2), Learning Rate (LR), and Number of Epochs. Because of the high number of variables, a DOE was run to determine the effect each variable had on the outcome. Several conclusions were drawn based on the results shown in Figure 19:

- Hidden Layer 1 & 2 had little direct effect on the results, while the Number of Epochs & Quality of Data had a significant effect.

- For the “good data only” set, a higher learning rate yielded the best results.
- Regardless of the data quality, maximizing the number of Epochs always provided better results.
- When HL2 was low, a lower LR yielded better results. When HL2 was high, a higher LR yielded better results.

Figure 19

Using settings based on the DOE results, a heuristic backpropagation learning model was created using uncontaminated data only. The results were analyzed by graphing the predicted blend ratios versus the actual blend ratios (see Figures 20 and 21). Overall, the results showed that backpropagation learning could estimate the blend ratio of a fuel sample with reasonable accuracy. When greater precision is required, backpropagation learning had a larger margin of error as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 20

Figure 21

When running Kohonen networks the variable inputs include:

- Number of Rows & Columns of Clusters
- Number of Epochs (or training cycles)
- Learning Rate (η = how fast or slow the network comes to a solution)
- And the quality of data (Use of the entire data set or of uncontaminated-good data only)

Just like in backpropagation learning, a DOE was run to determine the effect each variable had on the outcome (see Figure 22). Several conclusions were drawn based on the results:

- Rows & Columns were by far the main effect on the results.
- Because Epochs had such a small effect, the number of Epochs was minimized to reduce test time.

Figure 22

Using settings based on the DOE results, a heuristic Kohonen networks model was created. Unlike backpropagation learning, Kohonen networks do not have a similar output. The results are shown by how the model divides the data into clusters. The effectiveness of the model was judged by how well the clusters were divided by the actual blend ratios.

The data was run in two different ways. The first way was by setting the number of instances equal to the total number of samples. This was considered the “training data”, and returned the entire data set divided into clusters. Figure 23 shows the training data,

which had a very poor division of clusters. Only 2 of 12 blend ratios were divided into their own clusters; all other blend ratios were mixed among multiple clusters.

The second way that the data was run was by setting the number of instances < the number of samples. The program then created a model using the number of instances as training data, and ran the remaining samples through that model as “validation data”. The data output was the results only from the “validation data” which is shown in Figure 24. The pattern in this data is very similar to the training data in Figure 23, relatively random. Overall, these results show how poor of a fit Kohonen networks were to this particular application.

BLEND RATIO	Cluster												Grand Total
	0	3	9	30	37	40	49	61	70	81	94	99	
0.000%						4			2		2		8
0.904%						6			1	1	1		9
1.700%								2		4	1		7
3.236%						3		1	2	1	1		8
6.208%				3		1			1		4		9
11.641%				4				2		2			8
20.854%	6	1									2		9
33.733%						1				2			3
34.030%		6											6
50.357%												6	6
66.67%					3		4						7
100.00%			6										6
Grand Total	6	7	6	7	3	15	4	5	6	10	11	6	86

Table 1: Training Data

Count of Cluster	Cluster												Grand Total
	0	3	6	9	37	40	50	59	60	90	93		
0									1	2			3
0.904	1						1			1			3
1.7	1												1
3.236						1			1				2
6.208											3		3
11.641						1	1					1	3
20.854												3	3
33.733										1			1
34.03		1										2	3
50.357								2					2
66.67			1		2								3
100				3									3
Grand Total	2	1	1	3	2	2	2	2	2	7	6		30

Table 2: Validation Data

By setting the data output to be the contamination check results, it was possible to create a model that would predict if a fuel sample was corrupt and noisy or not. As you can see from the results from Backpropagation Neural Networks shown in Figure 23, there was a 99% success rate in predicting if the sample is contaminated or not.

Kohonen network results are shown in Figure 24; a 2x2 matrix was used with a very low number of epochs. The data was separated into 2 clusters and then compared to the actual separation between contaminated and uncontaminated samples. Surprisingly, Kohonen networks were very poor at classifying the samples as contaminated or not. In the best case it predicted with a 72% accuracy.

Figure 23

Figure 24

In conclusion:

- Back Propagating Neural Networks could accurately estimate the blend ratios 97% of the time using non-corrupt data. The accuracy degraded at blend ratios below 12%.
- Back Propagating Neural Networks were sufficient at determining corrupt and noisy samples, correctly classifying 99.1% of the samples.
- Kohonen Networks could not accurately classify the blend ratios or identify corrupt and noisy samples.

Comparison: GA vs NN

GAs proved especially useful, compared to NN, in the lower concentration region of the study where the differences in concentrations were much smaller. This is significant because many biodiesel users face situations in which the concentrations of the offered biodiesel products will be 0%, 2%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 50% and 100%. At the lower end of the concentrations there are many more offerings with much closer concentration values making accuracy a paramount concern.

GAs proved more effective at classifying noisy vs clean data. DiscipulusTM was able to achieve a hit rate of 100% on all training and validation data given a probability for

each class fixed at 0.5. The confidence level of DiscipulusTM classification was high on all but 10 samples of the total 108; these ten exhibited a confidence level of 50%.

Recommendations

The following experiments can be considered for future study related to biodiesel blend ratio identification and clustering in addition to and in parallel with the ongoing research summarized in this report:

- Incorporate statistical measures to better validate NN and GA results.
- A larger sample size would be more easy to work with and helpful for better validation.
- Diverse data collection techniques (FTIR, X-ray, color and other sources of spectrometry) to eliminate machine induced biases and for comparison.
- Incorporate TRIZ, DOE etc... to identify specific design constraints to evaluate in each GA or NN program.
- Provide sample data for after the fact testing of the formulated programs and teams. Attempt to incorporate this real time into the sampling process, as well as the contamination check.
- Investigate further into Back Propagating Neural Networks granularity at high blend ratios.
- Test the Back Propagating Neural Networks using blend ratios that were not used in training to determine the degree to which it acts as a lookup table (is it classifying the data or estimating it?)

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